

Mendelian randomization study on vitamin C and type 2 diabetes may be misleading

Harri Hemilä¹

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Comment on:

Zheng JS, Luan J, Sofianopoulou E, Imamura F, Stewart ID, Day FR, Pietzner M, Wheeler E, Lotta LA, Gundersen TE, Amiano P, Ardanaz E, Chirlaque MD, Fagherazzi G, Franks PW, Kaaks R, Laouali N, Mancini FR, Nilsson PM, Onland-Moret NC, Olsen A, Overvad K, Panico S, Palli D, Ricceri F, Rolandsson O, Spijkerman AMW, Sánchez MJ, Schulze MB, Sala N, Sieri S, Tjønneland A, Tumino R, van der Schouw YT, Weiderpass E, Riboli E, Danesh J, Butterworth AS, Sharp SJ, Langenberg C, Forouhi NG, Wareham NJ.

Plasma Vitamin C and Type 2 Diabetes: Genome-Wide Association Study and Mendelian Randomization Analysis in European Populations.

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Zheng et al. concluded from their Mendelian randomization study on plasma vitamin C effects on type 2 diabetes risk that “*a genetically higher level of plasma vitamin C was not significantly associated with type 2 diabetes risk or with glycemic traits*” [1, p 103].

In the potential limitations of the study, Zheng wrote that “*the low variability of plasma vitamin C explained by these SNPs [single-nucleotide polymorphisms] may limit the statistical power and precision for the MR analysis*” [1, p 104]. However, Zheng et al. did not consider this issue of power further in their paper.

Zheng reported that “*The variance of plasma vitamin C explained by the 11 lead SNPs was 1.87% on average*” [1, p 102]. From this figure, and the data about the plasma vitamin C means and SD levels available in the Zheng paper, we calculated that their Mendelian randomization study would correspond to the comparison of two population groups of equal size with vitamin C levels of 47.3 vs. 52.7 µM [2]. Such a comparison is not clinically relevant.

¹ Harri Hemilä, MD, PhD

Department of Public Health, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, FINLAND.

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/persons/harri-hemil%C3%A4>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

With low dietary vitamin C intakes, plasma levels can fall below 10 μM , whereas with high dietary intakes, plasma levels can increase to over 80 μM , see Fig. 1C in [3]. It is important to take into account this eightfold range of plasma vitamin C levels when considering the dose-health relationship in the community, but that was not done by Zheng et al. [1].

Low plasma vitamin C levels are not uncommon. Levels below 11 μM were reported, for example, in 25% of men and 16% of women from low-income populations in the UK [4], and in 13% of a US cohort [5]. In many population groups in less developed countries, such low vitamin C levels are even more common [6]. Thus, large segments of the population have vitamin C levels that are less than one fifth of the “low” plasma vitamin C level corresponding to the Zheng analysis.

Based on the large variation in the plasma levels of vitamin C in the population, the most relevant comparison is between low and high plasma levels, e.g., 10–20 μM vs. 60–100 μM . If a study compares small variations within the high intake range only, the comparison is uninformative about possible effects of vitamin C in the low intake range.

Vitamin C may, or may not, influence the risk of type 2 diabetes. However, the study by Zheng et al. is not informative about whether the risk of type 2 diabetes is increased with plasma vitamin C levels in the lower range of 10-20 μM .

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